

Evaluation of FYM and Inorganic NP Fertilizers on Yield Performance of Sweet Potato [*Ipomoea batatas* (L.) Lam] in Debub Ari District, Southwestern Ethiopia

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Abstract

Lack of appropriate recommendation rates of fertilizers is one of the major problems limiting yield production. A study was conducted to evaluate the effect of FYM and inorganic NP fertilizers on tuberous root yield and yield related parameters of sweet potato at Jinka Agricultural Research Center Station. The treatment consisted of three levels of N (0, 23 and 46 kg ha⁻¹), three levels of P (0, 20 and 40 kg ha⁻¹) and three levels of FYM (0, 2.5 and 5 t ha⁻¹). The experiment was laid out as a Randomized Complete Block Design in a factorial arrangement and replicated three times. Analysis of the results showed that the main effects of nitrogen ($P < 0.05$), phosphorous ($P < 0.05$) and farm yard manure ($P < 0.05$) showed significant difference on total tuber yield and fresh biomass but dry matter was non-significantly affected by the main effects of nitrogen ($P < 0.05$), phosphorous ($P < 0.05$) and farm yard manure ($P < 0.05$). The interaction effects of N ($P < 0.05$), P ($P < 0.05$) and farm yard manure ($P < 0.05$) showed significant difference on total tuber yield, fresh biomass and dry matter. Soil samples collected from the experimental field before treatment application showed sandy clay in texture, moderately acidic in reaction, very low in total nitrogen, low in available P, medium in organic carbon, and low cation exchange capacity. Maximum total tuber yield was recorded at the combined application of N, P and farm yard manure at the rates of 46 kg N ha⁻¹, 92 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ and 5 t FYM, respectively which was in statistical at parity with the application of 46 kg N ha⁻¹, 92 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ and 2.5t FYM whereas the minimum was obtained for the combined application of nil rates of all fertilizers. A maximum net return of 226477.6 ETB was obtained from plots receiving treatments of 46 kg N ha⁻¹, 92 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ and 5t FYM compared to the minimum net benefit (82404.9 ETB) from the control plots. However, the application of 46 kg N ha⁻¹, 92 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ and 2.5t FYM was also at par net benefit (223588.3 Eth-Birr) with those treatment. So, to minimize production cost and due to environmental friendly, combined application of 46 kg N ha⁻¹, 92 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ and 2.5t FYM is recommended. Sweet potato growers can also use 46 kg N ha⁻¹, 92 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ and 5t FYM as an alternative option for long term productivity of the soil.

Keywords: *FYM, Nitrogen, Sweet potato, Tuber.*

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Introduction

Sweet potato (*Ipomoea batatas* (L.) Lam), a member of Convolvulaceae family, is a perennial crop usually grown as an annual and a starchy staple food crop in the tropical, sub-tropical and frost free temperate climatic zones of the world (Onwueme and Sinha, 1991). It ranks fifth as the most important food crop after rice, wheat, maize and cassava in developing countries (Som, 2007). In sub Saharan Africa, sweet potato is the third most important root crop after cassava and yam. In this region of Africa, over 7 million tons (5% of global production) of sweet potato is produced annually (CSA, 2015).

The potential of sweet potato to guarantee food security is underestimated as its use is often limited to a substitute food in African countries. Sweet potato is valued for its roots which are boiled, fried, baked or roasted for humans or boiled and fed to livestock as a source of energy. The roots can also be processed into flour for bread making, starch for noodles as well as used as raw material for industrial starch and alcohol (Ukom et al., 2009).

In Ethiopia, sweet potato has been cultivated for many years and is important in diet where population growth is highest, land holding is least and threat of large scale starvation is ever present (Habtu, 1995). The crop is one of the root and tuber crops grown in Ethiopia, and it is the third important root crop next to Enset and Potato (Engida et al., 2009). The area covered and production of sweet potato in Ethiopia is increasing from time to time. However, its production is very limited to specific regions, like that of South Nation, Nationalities and Peoples, Oromia, and Amhara regions (Birhanu et al., 2014). Over 95% of the crop is produced in the south west, eastern and southern parts of Ethiopia where it has remained for centuries as one of the major subsistence crops especially in the periods of drought with low production (Endale et al., 1992). The national average yield of sweet potato was estimated to 45.65 t ha⁻¹, but the regional average yield of Southern Regional State was 22.31 t ha⁻¹ which had 23.34 t ha⁻¹ yield gap with the national average yield which implies lower productivity of the crop of the region (CSA, 2015).

Sweet potato is widely accepted and consumed in Southern Regional State, but its production and supply does not match since it is not extensively cultivated. Even among the few growers, sweet potato production is low. The total area of land covered by sweet potato in the region was only 22,767.29 ha and the total production was 508,152.8 t (CSA, 2015). Thus, Southern Regional State is among the least sweet potato producing regions in Ethiopia. A number of experiments were conducted in Ethiopia to determine the response of sweet potato to NP fertilizers. So far, the results of the experiments have showed that the plant does not respond to NP fertilizer application significantly as expected (Teshome and Nigussie, 2012). According to Nedunchezhiyan and Srinivasulu (2002), though sweet potato is grown in marginal and low fertility soil because of ready production of adventitious roots and trailing vines, it responds to application of nutrients. According to Gezahegn et al, (2014) integrated application of organic and inorganic fertilizer in sweet potato can enhance sweet potato yield and yield components.

Though farmers in sweet potato growing areas using farm yard manure for sweet potato production, they are not supported with optimum level of this fertilizer. Besides this, inorganic fertilizer effect on sweet potato production in this area is not systematically investigated. Considering the scarcity associated with inorganic fertilizer and limited amount of FYM, a systematic investigation into the effect of using commercial fertilizers and farmyard manure is of paramount importance for increasing production of sweet potato in the study area of the region where there is food insecurity and lack of improved soil

fertility technology to achieve high yield that genetically sweet potato can provide to fulfill the society's demand for this crop. To put solution for these problems, the objective of this study was to evaluate the effects of farm yard manure and inorganic fertilizers on yield and yield components of sweet potato and to determine optimum fertilizer rate for sweet potato production.

Materials and Methods

Description of Study Area

The experiment was conducted at the Research farm of Jinka Agricultural Research Centre during the main cropping season of 2018 and 2019. Jinka Agricultural Research Centre is located in Debub Ari District of South Omo Zone in South Ethiopia Region and 729 km south west of Addis Ababa, the capital city of Ethiopia at E 36°33'02.7" Longitude and N 05°46'52.0" Latitude and at an altitude of 1383 m.a.s.l (Fig 1). Long term weather data for the center revealed that the maximum and minimum monthly average temperature is 27.55 °C and 16.55°C respectively, while the mean annual rainfall of the area is 1274.67 mm. It is characterized by gentle to flat land features. The slope of the research field ranges from 0 to 5%. The rainfall pattern is erratic nature, and main rainy season extend from March to October interrupted by some dry period in May and sometime in June. The soils of the area are dominantly Cambisol, Sandy loam, Clay soil, and few alluvial types. Particularly, Jinka Agricultural research center station soil is characterized by texturally clay, the soil has low OM content (Mesfin et al., 2015).

Figure 1. Map of the study area

Planting Material

Sweet potato cultivar Awassa83 was selected, and which was maintained at JARC station for experiment. Two thirds of the vine in the soil for proper establishment was used. The cultivar was selected because of its adaptability, high yield potential, diseases resistance and early maturity.

Experimental Design and Treatments

Treatments consisted of three rates of FYM (0, 2.5, and 5 t ha⁻¹), three rates of N (0, 23, 46 Kg N ha⁻¹) and three rates of P (0, 20, 40 kg P ha⁻¹). There were total of 27 treatments including control, and the experiment was laid out in factorial arrangement in randomized complete block design (RCBD) and replicated three times per treatment. The vine cuttings was planted 45 degree incline to soil on ridges with spacing of 60cm and 30cm between rows and plants respectively. A plot size total of 12.96 m² (3.6m x 3.6m) was used as an experimental unit. Treatments were assigned to each plot randomly. Air-dried FYM collected from Jinka Research Center Station, which was stored for two months and applied on a dry weight basis a month before planting and thoroughly mixed with the soil. To minimize the loss and increase its efficiency half rate of N was applied as split at the time of planting and the remaining half N is applied at 60 days after planting whereas all P rate was applied as basal application during planting time. Urea, Diammonium phosphate, and TSP were used as inorganic N and P sources, whereas FYM was used as an organic fertilizer. A sweet potato variety called Awassa83 was used as a test crop. All recommended agronomic management practices were carried out during the crop growth period as per needed.

FYM and soil sampling analysis before planting

Farmyard manure was dried at 70°C for 48 hours and ground to a fine powder for analysis. Some nutrients composition of farm yard manure was analyzed in Jinka Agricultural Research Center soil laboratory. Soil samples was collected from the experimental field at the depth of 0-20 cm using auger in a Zig zag movement from ten spots before application FYM. Soil samples collected from the study site were air-dried and ground to pass 2 and 0.5 mm (for total N and OC) sieves, prepared and analyzed using standard soil laboratory procedures. The particle size distribution of the soil was analyzed using the Bouyoucos hydrometer method as outlined by Bouyoucos (1962). Soil textural classes were determined by using the textural triangle of the USDA system as described by Rowell (1994). The pH of the soils was measured in water suspension in a 1:2.5 (soil: water ratio) and measured potentiometrically using a glass-calomel combination electrode (Van Reeuwijk, 2002). The wet digestion method (Walkley and Black, 1954) was used to determine soil organic carbon (OC) content. Total soil N was determined using the Kjeldahl procedure by oxidizing the organic matter with sulfuric acid and converting total N into NH₄⁺ as ammonium sulfate (Jackson, 1967). Available soil P was determined by the Bray II method using ammonium fluoride and hydrochloric acid as an extracting solution and it was measured by spectrophotometer (Bray and Kurtz, 1945). The CEC of soil was determined from ammonium-saturated samples that are subsequently replaced by sodium (Na) from a percolating sodium chloride solution and reported as CEC (cmol⁽⁺⁾/kg) (Jackson, 1967).

Data Collection

All-important data were recorded and final harvesting was done when the leaves turned brown to determine the influence of the treatments on the tuberous yield of the crop under consideration. Plants in the central 4 rows in each plot was harvested for data collection like-total tuberous root yield, fresh total biomass, and tuberous root dry weight.

Partial Budget Analysis

Economic analysis was performed to investigate the economic feasibility of the treatments. Partial budget, dominance and marginal analyses was used. The average yield was adjusted 10% downwards to reflect the difference between the experimental plot yield and the yield of farmers which expect from the same treatment. The average open market price (Birr kg⁻¹) for sweet potato and the official prices of N, and P fertilizers was used for analysis. For a treatment to be considered a worthwhile option to farmers, the minimum acceptable rate of return (MARR) should be 100% (CIMMT, 1988), which is suggested to be realistic. This was support to make farmer recommendations from marginal analysis. The gross benefit

(GB) was calculated as average of adjusted root yield (kg/ha) × field price that farmers receive for the sale of the crop per kg. Total variable cost (TVC) was calculated as the sum of all production costs incurred in the farm. Net benefit (NB) or marginal return (MR) was calculated by subtracting total variable costs from the GB. Marginal rate of return (MRR) was calculated as the ratio of differences between net benefits of successive treatments to the difference between total variable costs of successive treatments. Treatments with high variable cost and with lower net benefit than the previous treatment were indicated as dominated.

Data analysis

The collected data from field experiment was analyzed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with the R software. Homogeneity of variance was tested using Barlett's test as described by Gomez and Gomez (1984). Thus, combined analysis of the two year data was accomplished. Differences among treatment means were compared using the least significant difference test at 5% level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Some Soil Physico-chemical Properties of the Experimental Site

The collected soil sample from the experimental field before planting was analyzed for some selected soil properties. It has moderately acidic soil reaction with a pH value of 5.8 for the surface of 0-20 cm depth. According to FAO (2000) the preferable pH ranges for most crops and productive soils are from 4 to 8. Thus, the experimental site was within the range for productive soils. Furthermore, the results showed a total nitrogen content of 0.04%, which is very low according to the rating by Landon (2013) who classified soils having total N of greater than 1.0% as very high, 0.5-1.0% high, 0.2-0.5% medium, 0.1-0.2% low and less than 0.1% as very low in total nitrogen content. Available phosphorus content of 9.4 mg kg⁻¹ which is low according to the rating by Tekalign (1991) who described soils with available P content of <10 ppm as low. The organic carbon content of the soil (1.63%) of the experimental site is medium. This shows that the soil needs additional external organic matter supply to nourish the plant. According to Landon (2013), top soils having CEC greater than 40 Cmol (+)/kg are rated as very high and 25-40 Cmol (+)/kg as high, 15-25, 5-15 and <5 Cmol (+)/kg of soil are classified as medium, low and very low, respectively. Thus, the soil of the study site with the CEC of 11.5 Cmol (+)/kg is rated as low. Similarly, the FYM sample applied to the experimental field before planting was analyzed for some selected chemical properties. It had pH of 7.2 which is neutral. Accordingly, the results obtained were total nitrogen content of 0.28% is rated as very high and available phosphorus content of 31 mg kg⁻¹ is also rated as high (Table 1).

Table 1. Selected Physicochemical Properties of the Soil and FYM in the Experimental Site before Planting

Soil Properties	Soil		FYM	
	Values	Rating	Values	Rating
Sand (%)	50			
Silt (%)	18			
Clay (%)	32			
Textural Class	Sandy clay			
Soil Reaction(pH)	5.8	moderately acidic	7.2	neutral
Total Nitrogen (%)	0.04	very low	0.28	very high
Available P (mg kg ⁻¹)	9.4	low	31	high
Organic Carbon (%)	0.95	medium	2.93	high
CEC (cmol ⁽⁺⁾ /kg)	11.5	low	45	very high

The main effects of nitrogen ($P < 0.05$), phosphorous ($P < 0.05$) and farm yard manure ($P < 0.05$) showed significant difference on total tuber yield and fresh biomass of sweet potato but dry matter was non-significantly affected by the main effects of nitrogen ($P < 0.05$), phosphorous ($P < 0.05$) and farm yard manure ($P < 0.05$). And also the analysis of variance revealed that the interaction effect of nitrogen and phosphorus ($P < 0.05$), and nitrogen and FYM ($P < 0.05$) and also phosphorus and FYM ($P < 0.05$) significantly influenced total tuber yield and fresh biomass.

Table 2. Main Effects of Nitrogen, Phosphorus, and FYM on Total Tuber Yield, Fresh Biomass and Dry Matter of Sweet Potato

Factor	Treatments	Total tuber yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Fresh biomass (kg ha ⁻¹)	Dry matter
Nitrogen (kg N ha ⁻¹)	0	19040b	20658c	50.960
	23	20827ab	23933b	50.007
	46	22557a	26576a	49.528
LSD (0.05)		2725.7	2478.8	NS
Phosphorus (kg P ha ⁻¹)	0	19194 b	21780b	48.403
	20	20420ab	24249ab	52.199
	40	22809a	25138a	49.894
LSD (0.05)		2725.7	2478.8	NS
FYM (t ha ⁻¹)	0	17272b	21548b	48.450
	2.5	21352a	23848ab	50.524
	5	23801a	25770a	51.522
LSD (0.05)		2725.7	2478.8	NS
CV (%)		23.98	19.13	14.85

Table 3. Interaction Effects of Nitrogen and Phosphorus on Total Tuber Yield and Fresh Biomass of Sweet Potato

Treatments	Total tuber yield (kg ha ⁻¹)			Fresh biomass (kg ha ⁻¹)		
	P (kg P ha ⁻¹)			P (kg P ha ⁻¹)		
	0	20	40	0	20	40
0	17752b	18739b	20629b	18825d	21689cd	21459cd
23	19112b	21300ab	22067ab	22287bcd	24657bc	24854abc
46	20718b	21222ab	25732a	24227bc	26401ab	29100a
LSD (0.05)	4721.0			4293.4		
CV (%)	23.98			19.13		

Table 4. Interaction Effects of Nitrogen and FYM on Total Tuber Yield and Fresh Biomass of Sweet Potato

Treatments	Total tuber yield (kg ha ⁻¹)			Fresh biomass (kg ha ⁻¹)		
	FYM (t ha ⁻¹)			FYM (t ha ⁻¹)		
	0	2.5	5	0	2.5	5
0	14236d	20282bc	22602abc	17627e	20665de	23681bcd
23	19050bc	20266bc	23164abc	23909bcd	22116cd	25773abc
46	18529cd	23507ab	25637a	23109cd	28762a	27857ab
LSD (0.05)	4721.0			4293.4		
CV (%)	23.98			19.13		

Table 5. Interaction Effects of Phosphorus and FYM on Total Tuber Yield and Fresh Biomass of Sweet Potato

Treatments	Total tuber yield (kg ha ⁻¹)			Fresh biomass (kg ha ⁻¹)		
	FYM (t ha ⁻¹)			FYM (t ha ⁻¹)		
	0	2.5	5	0	2.5	5
0	15110d	19849bc	22624ab	18251c	20328bc	26761a
20	17326cd	21505bc	22431ab	22524abc	26084a	24139ab
40	19379bcd	22701ab	26348a	23870ab	25132a	26411a
LSD (0.05)	4721.0			4293.4		
CV (%)	23.98			19.13		

Balanced application of nitrogen, phosphorus and farm yard manure can significantly increase sweet potato yield by promoting healthy foliage, robust root growth and optimal tuber formation. The interaction effects of N ($P < 0.05$), P ($P < 0.05$) and farm yard manure ($P < 0.05$) showed significant difference on total tuber yield, fresh biomass and dry matter.

Maximum total tuber yield of sweet potato were recorded at the combined application of N, P and farm yard manure at the rates of 46 kg N ha⁻¹, 92 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ and 5 t FYM, respectively which were in statistical at parity with the application of 46 kg N ha⁻¹, 92 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ and 2.5 t FYM (Table 2). This attributes to combination of farm yard manure with chemical fertilizer increases the essential soil micronutrients and promotes microbial population, which ultimately promotes the plant growth and production at sustainable basis (Mugwira and Murwira, 1998). The authors also reported that the use of organic manure is more beneficial when combined with inorganic fertilizers. This result is in line with the findings of Gezachew (2006) who showed that the interaction effect of compost and NP fertilizers significantly increased total and marketable tuber number of potato. Baghour *et al.* (2001) also reported that vegetative growth, yield and quality of onion significantly improved through organic and inorganic fertilizer application. Keeping the rate of nitrogen (urea) application at nil and increasing the rates of phosphate and farm yard manure did not result in consistent increases in total tuber yield of the sweet potato. However, when the rate of nitrogen was increased further to 46 kg ha⁻¹, increasing the rates of both phosphate and farm yard manure consistently increased total tuber yield. Thus, the maximum total tuber yields were obtained in response to the combined application of the highest rate of phosphate (92 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹) and the highest rate of farm yard manure (5 t ha⁻¹) with 46 kg N ha⁻¹. A combined application of N, P and farm yard manure at the rates of 46 kg N ha⁻¹, 92 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ and 5 t FYM was significantly increased total tuber yield of sweet potato by 195% over the control (no fertilizer). This might be due to FYM fertilizer along with in mineral fertilizer enhance all nutrient requirement of the plant. Similarly, Surindra (2009) showed that integrated nutrient supply of NPK and organic manures brings an excellent biochemical changes in soil structure, which ultimately promotes plant growth and production. In this study, the interaction effect of N, P and FYM produced significantly maximum total tuber yields indicating that the application of N, P and FYM fertilizers to be used for improving plant performance in the specified experimental site. And also similar to the findings of several researchers who found that increase in N levels significantly increased marketable storage root yields of potato in western and eastern parts of Ethiopia (Yibekal, 1998; Girma, 2001). Djalil and Dasril (2004) also reported that the amendment of soil with organic matter sources can increase the production of sweet potato tubers. This result corroborates with the study of Habtam (2012) who reported that increase in yield of crop might be due to increased dry matter production and its distribution in plant parts. Tekalign and Hammes (2005) also reported that the assimilation of dry matter and its distribution within the plant are important processes determining crop productivity. The results also confirmed that Sanchez and Jam (2002) who reported that integration of organic and mineral NP fertilizers sustains crop production due to positive interaction and complementarities between them.

Fresh above ground biomass was significantly influenced by the main effects of N, P and FYM ($P < 0.05$) and the interaction effect of N, P and FYM ($P < 0.05$) fertilizers. The maximum fresh biomass (32670 kg ha^{-1}) was obtained at the combined application of N, P and FYM fertilizers at 46 kg N ha^{-1} , $46 \text{ kg P}_2\text{O}_5 \text{ ha}^{-1}$ and 5 t FYM , respectively (Table 6). Keeping the rates of farm yard manure application at nil over all other rates of nitrogen to 46 kg N and phosphate to $92 \text{ kg P}_2\text{O}_5$ application increase fresh biomass yield. Similarly, at the nil rate of nitrogen, increasing the rates of phosphate to $92 \text{ kg P}_2\text{O}_5 \text{ ha}^{-1}$ and the rates farm yard manure to 5 t ha^{-1} significantly increased fresh biomass yield of the sweet potato. This finding is in agreement with the result of Maksoud *et al.* (1984) who found significantly increased marketable yield of garlic with increased N application. The analysis of variance also revealed that the interaction effect of N, P and farm yard manure significantly influenced dry matter. The maximum dry matter was recorded in response to the combined application of N, P and FYM fertilizers at 46 kg N ha^{-1} , $46 \text{ kg P}_2\text{O}_5 \text{ ha}^{-1}$ and 5 t FYM whereas the minimum was obtained for the combined application of nil rates of all fertilizers (Table 7).

Table 6. Interaction Effects of Nitrogen, Phosphorus, and FYM on Total Tuber Yield, Fresh Biomass and Dry Matter of Sweet Potato

Treatments		Total tuber yield (kg ha^{-1})			Fresh biomass (kg ha^{-1})		
N (kg ha^{-1})	P (kg ha^{-1})	FYM (t ha^{-1})			FYM (t ha^{-1})		
		0	2.5	5	0	2.5	5
0	0	9638f	17967def	19175cde	13076g	18611fg	24789b-f
	20	17138def	18905cde	19652b-e	20530ef	22855def	21682def
	40	15932ef	19975b-e	20980b-e	19275fg	20530ef	24573b-f
23	0	17714def	19565b-e	21058b-e	19203fg	19588fg	28071a-d
	20	18339cde	21731b-e	23830a-e	22726def	25442a-f	25802a-f
	40	21097b-e	20502b-e	24603a-d	23447c-f	24033b-f	27083a-e
46	0	16500def	20015b-e	22162a-d	22474def	22783def	27423a-e
	20	17978cde	22878a-e	24287a-d	21600def	24933b-f	32670a
	40	21110b-e	27626ab	28461a	25252a-f	30833abc	31214ab
LSD (0.05)		8177.0			7436.4		
CV (%)		23.98			19.13		

Table 7. Interaction Effects of Nitrogen, Phosphorus, and FYM on Total Tuber Yield, Fresh Biomass and Dry Matter of Sweet Potato

Treatments		Dry matter		
N (kg ha^{-1})	P (kg ha^{-1})	FYM (t ha^{-1})		
		0	2.5	5
0	0	43.19e	44.29de	48.17b-e
	20	49.80a-e	57.71abc	48.78b-e
	40	48.04b-e	47.25b-e	50.82a-e
23	0	47.25b-e	48.29b-e	50.75a-e
	20	56.14a-d	45.65cde	51.39a-e
	40	45.73cde	49.09b-e	52.44a-e
46	0	51.18a-e	51.06a-e	54.70a-e
	20	47.40b-e	58.82ab	62.12a
	40	46.21cde	53.65a-e	61.51ab
LSD (0.05)		12.21		
CV (%)		14.85		

The partial budget analysis of sweet potato is significantly affected by the combined application of nitrogen, phosphorus and farm yard manure (Table 8). A maximum net return of 226477.6 ETB was

obtained from plots receiving treatments of 46 kg N ha⁻¹, 92 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ and 5t FYM compared to the minimum net benefit (82404.9 ETB) from the control plots. From the economic point of view, it was apparent that the application of 46 kg N ha⁻¹, 92 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ and 5t FYM hit the highest point and more profitability than the rest of the other treatments. However, the application of 46 kg N ha⁻¹, 92 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ and 2.5t FYM was also at par net benefit (223588.3 Eth-Birr) with those treatments (Table 8). The result showed that the combined application of 46 kg N ha⁻¹, 92 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ and 2.5t FYM gives 3776.7%, which is well above the 100% minimum rate of return, which was considered as the best for the recommendation (Table 8). This treatment shows the maximum net benefit, relatively low variable cost, and acceptable marginal rate of return when compared with the other treatments. The best recommendation for treatments subjected to a marginal rate of return is not necessarily based on the highest marginal rate of return, rather based on the maximum net benefit, relatively low variable cost together with the minimum acceptable marginal rate of return becomes the tentative recommendation (CIMMYT, 1988).

Table 8. Economic (Partial Budget, Dominance and Marginal Rate of Return) Analysis of the Organic and Inorganic Fertilizers on Sweet Potato

Treatments			TY (kg ha ⁻¹)	10% adj TY (kg ha ⁻¹)	GM (ETB)	TVC (ETB)	NB (ETB)	DA	MRR (%)
N	P	FYM							
0	0	0	9638	8674.2	82404.9	0	82404.9		
23	0	0	17714	15942.6	151454.7	1165	150289.7	ND	582.0
46	0	0	16500	14850	141075	2330	138745	D	
0	20	0	17138	15424.2	146529.9	3017	143512.9	D	
23	20	0	18339	16505.1	156798.5	4182	152616.5	ND	781.4
0	0	2.5	20967	18870.3	179267.9	4250	175017.9	ND	294.2
46	20	0	17978	16180.2	153711.9	5347	148364.9	D	
23	0	2.5	18565	16708.5	158730.8	5415	153315.8	D	
0	40	0	15932	14338.8	136218.6	6034	130184.6	D	
46	0	2.5	20015	18013.5	171128.3	6580	164548.3	D	
23	40	0	21097	18987.3	180379.4	7199	173180.4	D	
0	20	2.5	19905	17914.5	170187.8	7267	162920.8	D	
46	40	0	21110	18999	180490.5	8364	172126.5	D	
23	20	2.5	21731	19557.9	185800.1	8432	177368.1	ND	770.2
0	0	5	19175	17257.5	163946.3	8500	155446.3	D	
46	20	2.5	22878	20590.2	195606.9	9597	186009.9	ND	2786.1
23	0	5	21058	18952.2	180045.9	9665	170380.9	D	
0	40	2.5	19975	17977.5	170786.3	10284	160502.3	D	
46	0	5	24162	21745.8	206585.1	10830	195755.1	ND	645.6
23	40	2.5	20502	18451.8	175292.1	11449	163843.1	D	
0	20	5	22652	20386.8	193674.6	11517	182157.6	D	
46	40	2.5	27626	24863.4	236202.3	12614	223588.3	ND	3776.7
23	20	5	23830	21447	203746.5	12682	191064.5	D	
46	20	5	24287	21858.3	207653.9	13847	193806.9	D	
0	40	5	25980	23382	222129	14534	207595	D	
23	40	5	24603	22142.7	210355.7	15699	194656.7	D	
46	40	5	28461	25614.9	243341.6	16864	226477.6	ND	2731.408

Note: N = Nitrogen, P = Phosphorus, FYM = Farm Yard Manure, TY = Tuber Yield, 10% adj TY = 10% adjusted Tuber yield, GM = Gross Margin, TVC = Total variable cost, NB = Net Benefit, DA = dominance analysis, D = Dominated, ND=non dominated

Conclusion

The finding of this study indicated that sweet potato well responded to the combined application of organic and inorganic fertilizers. Thus, information on fertility status of soils and crop response to different soil fertility management is very important to come up with profitable and sustainable crop production. The current study indicated that the combined use of FYM and inorganic fertilizers enhanced sweet potato productivity and yield through increasing total tuber yield, fresh biomass and dry matter by increasing nutrient uptake and utilization. Accordingly, considering the poor soil fertility management by resource poor smallholder farmers and the maximum cost of mineral fertilizers, combined application of FYM with mineral fertilizers at optimum rates is crucial to improve the soil and enhance productivity of sweet potato. So, to minimize production cost and due to environmental friendly, combined application of 46 kg N ha⁻¹, 92 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ and 2.5t FYM is recommended. Sweet potato growers can also use 46 kg N ha⁻¹, 92 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ and 5t FYM as an alternative option for long term productivity of the soil.

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